

THE DECLINE OF SOIL FERTILITY & THEIR MAINTENANCE

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Introduction

A significant challenge in global food security and agricultural productivity is the world's population expansion and the loss of arable land. After the Green Revolution, there was a significant increase in chemical fertilizers, the effect of which was seen on the soil fertility of the fields. In addition to increasing crop productivity, these chemical fertilizers have limited agricultural soil and had negative environmental effects, such as deteriorating air quality from the release of excessive amounts of greenhouse gases and aerosols, as well as contaminating soil and water bodies with heavy metals and excessive amounts of nutrients.

Additionally, excessive fertilizer use in the field can lead to soil degradation by depleting soil organic matter and decreasing soil fertility. Compared to earlier periods, two to three times as much fertilizer is now needed in the fields to produce crops. According to recent studies, approximately 2–10% of the nutrients from chemical fertilizers go from the soil to water bodies through surface runoff and subsurface leaching. This is a significant cause of eutrophication, which lowers plant fertility efficiency.

Factors affecting soil fertility

1. *Parent material:* If the parent material contains more nutrients, the soil developed from that rock contains more nutrients.
2. *Soil's inherent capacity to supply nutrients:* The nutrient content of soil varies with its nature. If the soil contains a large quantity of nutrients, it becomes more fertile.
3. *Climate and vegetation:* In heavy rainfall areas, the nutrients lost by leaching as well as the upper layer are eroded. Thus, the fertility of soil becomes low. Organic matter is oxidized in high temperatures (tropical regions), so that place fertility becomes low.

Fig: Schematic representation of loss of plant nutrients from the soil

4. *Topography:* The fertility of level lands is more because the nutrients of high land in soluble form are deposited, especially in low land.
5. *Physical condition of soil:* The physical state of the soil should be appropriate for its development and growth. For example, aeration is necessary for both plant growth and the healthy operation of microbes. Both processes are impacted by an inadequate oxygen supply, which causes organic matter to decay improperly and nutrients to not change into forms that plants can use.
6. *Microorganism and organic matter:* The soil containing more organic matter becomes more fertile while soil microorganisms bring the unavailable nutrients from their available form through various processes.
7. *Cropping system:* Cultivation of the same crop year after year in the same field decreases the fertility of soil. So, we do crop rotation instead of this.

Maintenance of soil fertility

The following things must be properly followed to increase the fertility of the soil.

- ✓ Choose wisely the suitable crop for suitable for a particular land. Practical experience will be helpful in this regard.

- ✓ Different crops should be grown each year because if we grow the same crop in the same field year after year, the soil's specific nutrients will be depleted and its fertility will decline.
- ✓ Weed grown in a particular land competes with crops for nutrients absorbs the available plant nutrients and makes the soil unfertile for that crop. So, it is necessary to control the weeds in time.
- ✓ Crop growth is hampered by the amount of soil moisture. While insufficient moisture limits germination and plant growth, excessive moisture in the soil results in the leaching of nutrients. Therefore, the soil should be kept at its optimum moisture content.
- ✓ Maintenance of proper acidity and alkalinity of soil because the availability of plant nutrients heavily depends on the pH of the soil. Generally, soil pH 6.0-7.5 is acceptable for most plants, as most nutrients become available in this pH range. To improve the pH of acidic soils, lime is frequently used, and in alkaline soil, gypsum is frequently used.
- ✓ Avoid excessive tillage, because it leads to high erosion, accelerating surface runoff, disrupting soil structure, soil biology, and organic matter level, thus leading to loss of nutrients at the soil surface. To protect soil and soil nutrients farmers can shift to a no-till or reduced tillage system.
- ✓ Cultivation of cover crops such as cowpea, sweet potato, etc., to make a cover on the surface of the soil, which reduces soil erosion and leaching loss of nutrients.
- ✓ Application of green manure, compost, vermicompost, farmyard manure, and organic or crop residues. The addition of that increases the organic matter and nutrient content of the soil. As a result, the fertility of the soil is increased.
- ✓ A lesser amount of nutrients is found in manures. Therefore, we should use fertilizers to suit plant needs. Although fertilizer application does not improve soil fertility, it can help plants meet their needs.
- ✓ Follow an integrated nutrient approach rather than only organic or inorganic fertilizer uses. This makes benefits and makes soils more fertile.

- ✓ Always apply fertilizer after soil testing. When farmers apply fertilizers incorrectly, they damage soil and water resources in addition to reducing agricultural production, while precise fertilizer and amendment applications are tailored to optimize crop yield and soil quality.

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